

EFFECT OF CARBON NANOTUBES CONTENT ON THE FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF PP/EPDM/MWCNT BLEND NANOCOMPOSITES UNDER DYNAMIC AND QUASI-STATIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Effect of multiwall carbon nanotube (MWCNT) content on the fracture toughness and deformation behaviour of polypropylene/ethylene–propylene–diene terpolymer/multi walled carbon nanotube (PP/EPDM/MWCNT) with and without maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene (PP-g-MA) is studied using dynamic (impact test) and quasi-static loading (EWF; essential work of fracture method) tests.

The rheological test results indicate that fluid-solid transition composition for un-compatible and compatibilized blend nanocomposites is 2 wt% and 1 wt% MWCNT, respectively. From transmission electron microscopic (TEM) images, it was observed that interconnected MWCNTs network forms after the rheological percolation threshold.

The results show that increasing the MWCNT content has a beneficial effect on the fracture toughness under impact test (dynamic loading) and negative effect on the fracture toughness under EWF test (quasi-static loading). Fractography studies reveal that these contradictory findings are attributed to the effect of MWCNT content increasing on the different dominant fracture toughness mechanisms which are active under high speed and low speed fracture test (i.e. crazing and shear yielding, respectively). However, presence of PP-g-MA improves the fracture toughness under both studied test condition.

1 INTRODUCTION

Outstanding properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) such as high Young's modulus and excellent electrical and thermal conductivity make it as ideal class of inclusions. In recent decades, CNT has been used to improve mechanical, physical, electrical or other functional properties of polymers and polymeric blends, due to these outstanding properties [1-3]. Many studies have been done on the evaluation of fracture toughness of nanocomposites reinforced by the CNT through dynamic and quasi-static loading test methods [1-8]. However, few studies have compared the fracture behavior and failure mechanisms of these nanocomposites under low and high speed test methods.

The main objective of this work is to study the effect of MWCNT content on the fracture behavior of PP/EPDM blends under dynamic and quasi-static loading condition. The effect of maleic anhydride-grafted polypropylene (PP-g-MA) as a compatibilizer on the toughness was also studied. The main focus of this study was to get insight into the effect of interconnected MWCNTs network formation on the fracture toughness of the blend nanocomposites under low speed and high speed test conditions.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS

The blend-nanocomposites prepared by melt-mixing of isotactic polypropylene (PP – SI080) was supplied by Polynar Petrochemical Company, Tabriz, Iran, and EPDM-KEP270 with density of 0.96 g/cm³ (ENB content= 4.5 wt %, ethylene content= 57 wt %) was provided by Kumho Polychem Company, South Korea. The specifications of used MWCNT are as follow: average diameter = 9.5 nm, average length of nanotubes = 1.5 μm and purity higher than 90% that was supplied

by Nanocyl. The used PP-g-MA as a compatibilizer had MFI value of about 80 g/10 min (180 C/ 2.16 kg) and 1.2 wt% of grafted maleic anhydride.

2.2 PREPARATION OF BLEND NANOCOMPOSITES

Blend nanocomposites were prepared in an internal mixer (Brabender W50EHT) at 180 °C, rotor speed of 60 rpm and 12 min total mixing time. For all the samples, the weight ratio of PP to EPDM was set at 80 to 20 wt%. To study the effect of MWCNT content, 0.5, 1, 2 and 3wt% of MWCNT was used to prepare the samples. In each compatibilized blend nanocomposite, the selected amount of PP-g-MA is twice the MWCNT content.

2.3 INSTRUMENTS AND TECHNIQUES

The flow behavior and melt linear viscoelastic properties blend nanocomposites were investigated by using a rheometric mechanical spectrometer (RMS; UDS 200, Anton Paar) equipped with parallel plate geometry (diameter=25 mm, gap= 1mm). The frequency sweep tests were performed in the range of 0.1-625 s⁻¹ at temperature of 190°C and with amplitude of 1% to maintain the response of materials in the linear viscoelastic regime.

The notched Izod impact strength (J/m) was evaluated by a GT7045-I (Gotech) impact tester according to ASTM D256 and five repeated tests were taken for each composition and mean values were recorded. All fractures for EWF test were performed with a crosshead speed of 5mm/min and clamped length of 40mm using a Zwick/Roell tensile testing machine (Z 010). At least five specimens were tested for each ligament length and data reduction followed the recommendation of the ESIS-TC4 group [9]. The dimension of EWF test samples were 80×23×1 mm and the notches were inserted using a sharp razor blade to obtain double edge notched tension (DENT) specimens with a series of ligament length. All these tests were conducted at ambient temperature (23 °C).

A HITACHI S-4160 field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) instrument was used for morphological studies on the fractured surfaces of impact and EWF tests. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed on a Philips EM208 microscope (Netherlands), operated at 100 kV.

2.4 ESSENTIAL WORK OF FRACTURE METHODOLOGY

EWF test method proposed first by Broberg [9] and developed by Cotterell and Reddel [10] and Karger-Kocsis [11-13] is a popular method for studying the fracture behavior of ductile polymeric materials. In this method the total energy required to fracture (W_f) can be divided into the essential work of fracture (W_e) consumed in the inner fracture process zone (IFPZ) to create new surface and non-essential work of fracture (W_p) dissipated in the outer plastic deformation (OPDZ). The related zones are shown schematically in case of a deeply double-edge notched specimen in Fig. 1. The relationship between work of fracture and its components can be written as follow:

$$W_f = W_e + W_p \quad (1)$$

By assuming that W_e is proportional to the ligament area, and W_p is proportional to the volume of plastic zone, the relationship between specific terms can be defined as follows:

$$W_f = w_e \times l \cdot t + \beta w_p \cdot \times .l^2 \cdot t \quad (2)$$

$$w_f = w_e + \beta w_p \cdot l \quad (3)$$

where w_f is the specific total work of fracture, l is the ligament length, t is the thickness of the sample and β is the plastic shape factor depending on the geometry of the plastic zone.

Figure 1: Deeply double-edge notched specimen and the different energy dissipation zones involved.

The total work of fracture, W_f , can be determined by integration of the area under force-displacement curves for each specimen. According to Eq. 3, the specific total work of fracture is a linear function of the ligament size. Therefore w_e can be determined from the interception of the linear regression line, fitted to the $w_f - l$ graphs with y-axis and the slope of this line is βw_p .

As discussed by Karger-Kocsis et al. [13] the total work of fracture can be partitioned at the maximum load as the summation of two contributing terms: a term W_y related to the yielding of ligament area and another term W_n associated with the subsequent necking and tearing. Therefore it can be written:

$$W_f = W_y + W_n \quad (4)$$

The specific terms (w_y and w_n) can be expressed as a function of ligament length similar to Eq. 3, as follows:

$$w_f = w_y + w_n = (w_{e,y} + \beta_y w_{p,y} \cdot l) + (w_{e,n} + \beta_n w_{p,n} \cdot l) \quad (5)$$

Where $w_{e,y}$ is the specific essential yielding-related work of fracture, $w_{e,n}$ is the specific essential tearing work, $w_{p,y}$ is volumetric energy dissipated during yielding and $w_{p,n}$ is dissipated plastic work during tearing and necking. β_y and β_n are geometric factors related to the shape of the plastic zone during the yielding and necking, respectively. By comparing Eq. 3 and Eq. 5, it can be concluded that:

$$w_e = w_{e,y} + w_{e,n} \quad (6)$$

$$\beta w_p = \beta_y w_{p,y} + \beta_n w_{p,n} \quad (7)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 RHEOLOGICAL TESTS

Fig.2 shows the storage modulus (G') and complex viscosity (η^*) as functions of angular frequency (ω) for blend nanocomposites containing different percentages of MWCNT with and without PP-g-MA. The results show that both storage modulus and complex viscosity of the uncompatibilized and compatibilized blend nanocomposites increase with the increase in MWNT content.

Figure 2: A) Storage modulus (G') and B) complex viscosity (η^*) versus angular frequency (ω) for blend nanocomposites with and without PP-g-MA.

The increase of storage modulus with percentage of MWCNT at high frequencies indicates that MWCNTs act as reinforcing agents in the blend nanocomposites and the stress transfers properly and homogeneously from the matrix to the nano particles. Specifically in the case of the sample with 0.5 wt% MWNT, at low frequencies PP chains are fully relaxed and exhibit like homopolymer terminal behavior. With increasing nanotube content, dependence of (G) on angular frequency at low frequency is limited and a plateau zone develops due to transition from liquid-like to solid-like viscoelastic behavior. This behavior can be linked to the formation of an interconnected network of MWCNTs in

the matrix [1]. Hence as the nanotube content increases, nanotube–nanotube interactions begin to dominate, and lead to percolation and the formation of an interconnected structure in the PP matrix. It can be clearly observed that the percolation threshold of MWCNTs for compatibilized and uncompatibilized blend-nanocomposites is about 1wt% and 2wt%, respectively.

TEM images of the PP/EPDM/MWCNT with 0.5 wt% and 3 wt% confirm the results of rheological analysis and show that in the sample with 3 wt% MWCNT, the interconnected MWCNTs network has formed.

Figure 3: TEM images of the un-compatible PP/EPDM/MWCNT A) 0.5 wt% and B) 3 wt% MWCNT content

3.2 IMPACT STRENGTH

Fig. 4 shows the results of impact strength of the blend nanocomposites. It reveals that with increasing MWCNT content, impact strength for the blend nanocomposites increases. The results also indicate that the impact strength for the compatibilized samples is higher than uncompatibilized ones. This may be attributed to the effect of PP-g-MA on the improvement of interfacial adhesion between PP and MWCNTs that leads to better dispersion of nano particles in the matrix that has been reported by the author [14, 15] and also confirmed in the rheological section.

Figure 4: Notched Izod impact strength of blend nanocomposites

Izod impact fractured surfaces of the un-compatible and compatibilized blend-nanocomposites (Fig. 5) indicate that by increasing the percentage of nanoparticle phase, the size of the voids remaining by the pulling out of rubber particles during the fracture process, has been diminished. Based on close examination of the impact fractured surface (Fig. 6) and the results of previous works [14, 16], this could be related to the presence of MWCNTs at the interface of PP and EPDM, as well as the occurrence of the nano-bridging mechanism, due to the formation of a nanoparticle network that acts as an energy consuming mechanism under the Impact fracture test. Presence of nanoparticles in the matrix, especially at higher MWCNT content, may have a hindrance effect on the coalescence of rubber phase during melt mixing that causes reduction in the size of dispersed rubber particles in the blend nanocomposites. Formation of interconnected MWCNTs network and decreasing the size of rubber particles may lead to efficient stress transfer from the matrix to MWCNTs and promote the crack and craze deviation mechanisms that is the main deformation mechanism under dynamic loading [14,16].

Figure 5: SEM images of impact fractured surfaces of a) PP/EPDM/MWCNT (80/20/0.5), b) PP/EPDM/PP-g-MA/MWCNT (80/20/1/0.5), c) PP/EPDM/MWCNT (80/20/1), d) PP/EPDM/PP-g-MA/MWCNT (80/20/2/1), e) PP/EPDM/MWCNT (80/20/3) and f) PP/EPDM/PP-g-MA/MWCNT (80/20/6/3)

Figure 6: SEM image of impact fractured surfaces of PP/EPDM/MWCNT (80/20/2)

3.3 EWF TEST

The results of essential and non-essential work of fractured and the splitting parameters for the blend nanocomposites (Table 1) show that increasing the MWCNT percentage causes a decrease in the essential work of fracture (w_e) and specific essential yielding-related ($w_{e,y}$) and the necking-related work of fracture ($w_{e,n}$) and an increase of the non-essential work of fracture (βw_p). The presence of PP-g-MA increases both the w_e and βw_p parameters of the blend-nanocomposites due to decreasing the size of large aggregates and increasing the number of dispersed individual MWCNT ropes [15]. However, after a determined amount of MWCNT, the compatibilized and uncompatibilized samples exhibit brittle-like fracture under quasi-static loading. The blend nanocomposites with more than 2 wt% MWCNT exhibited βw_p value close to zero with unacceptable correlation coefficient of the linear regression. Because of the unacceptable correlation coefficient and considering the non-self-similarity of the load-displacement curves (not shown here) it can be concluded that the fracture toughness of these samples cannot be evaluated by the EWF test method [9].

Fractography studies (Fig. 7) show that with increasing MWCNT content, shear yielding as a main fracture mechanism of samples under the quasi-static loading, is restricted. It can be related to the hindering effect of carbon nanotubes network on the ligament shear yielding [15, 16]. It is the main reason for decreasing the w_e and $w_{e,y}$ with any increase in MWCNT content. As discussed in our previous work [15, 16], the MWCNTs in the PP matrix could promote two different mechanisms: 1) craze and crack initiation by the MWCNT aggregates in the PP matrix and 2) arresting the propagating crack by the individual MWCNT impregnated fibrils. The former mechanism could bring about a lower w_e (term related to resistance to crack initiation) and the latter mechanism could induce higher βw_p (term related to resistance to crack propagation) for the blend nanocomposites.

Whereas the main fracture mechanisms under the EWF test are cavitation and/or debonding of the rubber particles followed by shear yielding of the PP matrix between ligaments [15], so the presence of dispersed MWCNTs in the matrix which have hindering effect on the shear yielding process cause a decrease in the fracture toughness under quasi-static loading.

On the contrary, whereas the main fracture mechanisms under the impact test are voids generated by cavitation and/or debonding of the rubber particles and act on MWCNT aggregates as craze initiation sites which lead to enhancing the crazing in the PP matrix [14], so dispersed MWCNTs in the matrix which act as craze and crack initiators cause increased fracture toughness of the samples under dynamic loading condition. Formation of interconnected MWCNTs network has an excessive effect on the impact strength of blend nanocomposites due to the outstanding mechanical properties of MWCNTs.

	Samples	w_e	βw_p	$w_{e,y}$	$\beta_y w_{p,y}$	$w_{e,n}$	$\beta_n w_{p,n}$
		N/mm	N/mm^2	N/mm	N/mm^2	N/mm	N/mm^2
Un-compatible Blend nanocomposites	80/20/0.5	7.8±0.6	2.8±0.2	2.2±0.12	0.6±0.05	5.6±0.3	2.2±0.18
	80/20/1	4.3±0.5	3.5±0.12	1.1±0.1	0.53±0.0.3	3.2±0.7	2.97±0.2
	80/20/2	Not applicabile					
	80/20/3	Not applicabile					
Compatible Blend nanocomposites	80/20/1/0.5	13.2±0.6	3.3±0.2	3.6±0.12	0.8±0.05	9.6±0.5	2.5±0.2
	80/20/2/1	6.5.8±1	4.1±0.25	1±0.23	0.97±0.05	5.5±1	3.13±0.2
	80/20/4/2	Not applicabile					
	80/20/63	Not applicabile					

Table 1: The results of essential and non-essential work of fracture and splitting the essential and non-essential work of fracture into yielding and necking and tearing for all the blend nanocomposites

Figure 7: SEM images of EWF fractured surfaces of PP/EPDM/MWCNT with A) 0.5 wt%, B) 1 wt%, C) 2 wt% and D) 3 wt%.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of MWCNT content on the fracture behaviour and deformation mechanisms of PP/EPDM/MWCNT blend nanocomposites with and without PP-g-MA were studied using the Impact strength test and EWF methodology and confirmed by using electron microscopy analysis.

The results showed that the increase of MWCNT content is beneficial for increasing the Izod impact fracture toughness of the blend-nanocomposites through formation of interconnected MWCNTs network and decreasing the size of rubber particles. On the other hand, the results of the EWF test showed that the increase of the MWCNT phase has negative effects on the fracture toughness through hindrance effect on the matrix fibril yielding and necking. It was demonstrated that this contradiction originates from different dominant toughening mechanisms in the PP matrix under the Izod impact test (crazing mechanism) and the EWF test (shear yielding mechanism). By increasing the percentage of the MWCNT phase and formation of interconnected MWCNTs network, crazing and shear yielding deformation mechanisms in the PP matrix decreased and increased, respectively. Other toughening mechanisms induced by the MWCNT phase such as nanobridge mechanisms were also evidenced in the samples and discussed.

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